

HIGH VELOCITY IMPACT TESTS ON STITCHED GRAPHITE/EPOXY LAMINATES

Lopresto¹ V., Santoro² D. and Caprino¹ G.

¹ *University of Naples "Federico II", Department of Materials and Production Engineering, Piazzale Tecchio, 80, 80125 Naples.*

² *Alenia Aeronautica S.p.A., Viale dell'Aeronautica, 80038 Pomigliano d'Arco.*

SUMMARY: Stitched graphite/epoxy laminates, having thicknesses in the range 1.5 to 6 mm, were subjected to ballistic impact. Two steel spheres, 12.7 mm and 20 mm in diameter, were used as bullets during the tests, carried out at two different speeds. From the results, the effect of thickness on the perforation energy was similar to what observed in low velocity impact. However, a different relationship was seemingly verified between the perforation energy and the projectile diameter, passing from low to high velocity. The delamination extent was strongly influenced by the bullet speed, with lower damage areas pertaining to high velocity; however, when sufficiently thick specimens were considered, the delaminated area was unaffected by speed.

KEYWORDS: ballistic impact, stitched, perforation, delaminated area.

INTRODUCTION

In the last years, many different methods, encompassing thermoplastic matrices, interlayers, Z-pinning, and through-the-thickness stitching, have been proposed to increase the damage resistance of composite laminates, giving rise to a better damage tolerance of these materials [1]. Among all these technologies, stitching appears one of the most promising [2]. However, some drawbacks of the stitching technique, consisting of loss in in-plane properties, have also been evidenced [3].

A further disadvantage of stitching, concerning the shielding capacity of composites, has been highlighted quite recently: it has been shown that the perforation energy of stitched laminates can suffer a considerable reduction under both low [4] and high velocity conditions [5]. In [5], where the better damage tolerance offered by stitching was also verified, it was noted that the choice of stitched or non-stitched laminates should be based on whether the design requirement is improved damage tolerance or improved shielding ability.

Unfortunately, not much data are available in the literature on the perforation behaviour of stitched laminates, especially in the domain of high velocity impact. This is the topic of the present work, where the thickness and projectile diameter effect on the perforation energy was faced. Comparing the results obtained with those of previous tests [4], carried out at low velocity, some analogies and some differences were found in the material behaviour, concerning both the dependence of the perforation energy on the test parameters and the development of delaminated area.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The ballistic impact tests were carried out on stitched CFRP laminates made of non-crimp fabric blocks. Each block, indicated by the symbol B hereafter, consisted of five tape plies of unimpregnated carbon 6K HTA fibres oriented along the directions 0° , -45° , 0° , $+45^\circ$, 90° , respectively. To have available laminates of different thickness, different numbers of dry basic blocks, according to the stacking sequence $[B_n]_s$, with $n = 1$ to 4, were used. Then, the stitching operation was performed, using Kevlar 29 yarns of 1600 denier. The stitching spacing and pitch were 5 mm. Finally, a resin film infusion technology was adopted for fibre impregnation, using a Fiberite Cytec 977-2 epoxy resin. The material was cured in autoclave under vacuum following the matrix supplier recommendations. The nominal thicknesses t of the cured panels were $t = 1.5, 3, 4.5$ and 6 mm and the fibre content by volume about 55%. From the laminates, square specimens 200 mm in side were cut by a diamond saw. The specimens were equipped on the back face with two strain gauges, each oriented parallel to one of the principal directions of the specimen and located 30 mm far from the impact point. The high velocity impact tests were carried out using the instrumented gas gun schematically shown in Fig. 1. In the apparatus, the incident speed is measured by a timer, triggered by the projectile cutting two light beams located into the barrel and provided by infra-red LEDs and photo-diode sensors.

The samples, clamped on a circular ring with a window 80 mm in diameter, were struck at the centre by a spherical hard steel projectile 12.7 mm in diameter, D_p , whose nominal velocity $V_o = 129$ m/s was set by adjusting the compressed air pressure.

In order to study the effects of the impactor diameter and speed, a limited amount of tests was also performed using $D_p = 20$ mm and $V_o = 65$ m/s. Table I shows the matrix of the tests scheduled.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the air gun used for the ballistic impact tests.

From Fig. 1, the annular ring supporting the target was fixed by four cylindrical rods 500 mm long to an instrumented catcher located on a back rigid support. In case of perforation, the projectile residual velocity was evaluated using the signals from the instrumented rods and the back landing pad. In case of rebound, the residual velocity could not be measured.

After each test, the samples were visually inspected to assess possible damage. Finally, they were ultrasonically C-scanned, to detect the extent of delaminated area.

Table I – Matrix of the experimental tests.

t (mm)	D _p (mm)	V _o (m/s)	Perforation
1.5	12.7	129	Yes
3.0	12.7	129	Yes
4.5	12.7	129	Yes
6.0	12.7	129	No
3.0	20	129	Yes
3.0	12.7	65	No

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the last column in Table I, perforation was actually achieved for all the test conditions adopted, except for $t=6$ mm and $V_o=65$ m/s. For the perforated samples, the perforation energy U_p was evaluated through the formula:

$$U_p = \frac{m}{2} (V_o^2 - V_r^2) \quad (1)$$

where m is the projectile mass, and V_r the residual velocity of the projectile. The results are graphically shown by the white symbols in Fig. 2, where the perforation energy is reported against the specimen thickness. In the figure, the experimental data are identified by the label “a/b”, where “a” is the projectile diameter (in mm), and “b” its velocity (in m/s).

Fig. 2: Perforation energy, U_p (white symbols) and impact energy, U_o (black symbols) for the specimens tested, against panel thickness, t . Theoretical predictions based on eq. (2), where the K and α values deriving from low velocity tests on stitched laminates were used.

Of course, the energy necessary for perforation increases with increasing both t and D_p . In particular, looking at the effect of thickness, doubling the latter results in a more than doubled U_p value. Apparently, this qualitative trend is common to high as well as low velocity impact. In fact, similar conclusions can be drawn from data obtained at low velocity, available in the literature [4,6].

Fig. 3: Experimental perforation energy measured at low and high velocity under similar constraint and projectile diameter conditions. Panel thickness $t=3$ mm.

In [4], low-velocity impact tests were carried out on the 3 mm, 4.5 mm, and 6 mm thick laminates considered here, using a hemispherical indenter 19.8 mm in diameter. Comparing the results obtained with previous data, concerning non-stitched CFRPs, it was concluded that stitching adversely affects the perforation energy, lowering it by about 30% with respect to classical laminates.

The constraint conditions adopted in [4] were slightly different from those used in this work, since the specimens were clamped in a circular support 50 mm in diameter. Nevertheless, as a first approximation, the effect of the impact speed on U_p can be evaluated by suitably comparing selected results obtained in [4] with those generated within the present work. This is done in Fig. 3, where the experimental perforation energy of the 3 mm thick samples under low and high velocity conditions is plotted. The impactor diameter is 19.8 mm and 20 mm for low and high velocity, respectively. From the figure, U_p is sensibly the same, suggesting that the material behaviour is substantially insensitive to the loading rate.

Of course, a direct comparison of the data in [4] with those found here could not be possible, because of the difference in the impactor diameter adopted in the two series of tests. However, if the hypothesis of a material response independent of the velocity is accepted, one must conclude that models valid in the case of low velocity also hold for high velocity impact.

In [6], the following empirical relationship was proposed in order to calculate the perforation energy as a function of the specimen thickness and tup diameter:

$$U_p = K \cdot (t \cdot V_f \cdot D_p)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

In eq. (2), V_f is the fibre volume fraction, and α , K , two constants only depending on the fibre type. In particular, for non-stitched CFRPs, the values $\alpha=1.44$ and $K=0.45 \text{ J/mm}^{2\alpha}$ were found in [6].

Eq. (2) was also applied in [4] to the stitched laminates subjected to low velocity impact. A good correlation between predictions and experimental results was shown retaining $\alpha=1.44$, and putting $K=0.32 \text{ J/mm}^{2\alpha}$. The theoretical predictions deriving from these values are represented by the solid and dashed line in Fig. 2 for $D_p=20 \text{ mm}$ and $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$, respectively. Clearly, a good agreement is found between theory and experiments, when the larger impactor diameter is concerned. This is anticipated, due to the coincidence of the perforation energies highlighted in Fig. 3. However, Fig. 2 also reveals that U_p is substantially underestimated for $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$, although the theoretical curve follows the trend of the experimental points.

Fig. 4: Damage visible on the: a) front face, and, b) back face of a specimen 6 mm in thickness after impact with $V_o=129 \text{ m/s}$. projectile diameter $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$.

Fig. 5: Damage visible on the: a) front face, and, b) back face of a specimen 3 mm in thickness after impact with $V_o=65 \text{ m/s}$. projectile diameter $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$.

That the actual U_p in the case of $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$ is higher than predicted by the dashed line in Fig. 2 is also qualitatively inferred from the results of the non-perforated samples. On the basis of the curve, the 6 mm thick specimens should be very near to perforation, or even beyond this limit. In fact, none of the three specimens tested under these conditions was perforated, although a severe damage was found after test, with a clean hole clearly visible on the front face (Fig. 4a), and extensive delamination and fibre failure on the back face (Fig. 4b). Further, no damage was revealed by the visual inspection (Fig. 5a and 5b) of the panels with $t=3 \text{ mm}$ ($V_o=65 \text{ m/s}$, see Table I). This observation is difficult to accept, considering that, according to

the dashed line in Fig. 2, the perforation energy was quite near to (about 77% of) the mean impact energy level utilized in the tests.

Fig. 6: Perforation energy, U_p (white symbols) and impact energy, U_o (black symbols) for the specimens tested, against panel thickness, t . Theoretical predictions based on eq. (2), where the K and α values deriving from low velocity tests on classical laminates were used.

The same data discussed in Fig. 2 are reported in Fig. 6. The only difference is in the theoretical curves, which were drawn using the α and K values obtained from the low velocity impact tests on classical laminates discussed in [6] ($\alpha=1.44$ and $K=0.45 \text{ J/mm}^2\alpha$). Quite surprisingly, when this is done, the points concerning the perforation energy in the case of $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$ are well represented. From a physical standpoint, this would indicate that the behaviour of non-stitched and stitched laminates is sensibly the same. The trend of the dashed line in Fig. 5 is also in better qualitative agreement than the corresponding curve in Fig. 2 with the visual damage features in Figs. 4 and 5: according to the predictions in Fig. 6, the impact energy level for $t=6 \text{ mm}$ and of $D_p=12.7 \text{ mm}$ (Fig. 4) is approximately 72% of the perforation energy, which would clarify why no perforation was experimentally observed under these test conditions. Further, the impact energy for $t=3 \text{ mm}$ and $V_o=65 \text{ m/s}$ is about 55% of the theoretical U_p value, possibly explaining the absence of visible damage in Fig. 5.

From the solid line in Fig. 6, it is also seen that U_p is highly overestimated for $D_p=20 \text{ mm}$. Therefore, the results presented seem to indicate that eq. (2) is successful in modeling the thickness effect on the perforation energy, whereas it fails when the influence of the projectile diameter is concerned. Of course, in this hypothesis the coincidence highlighted in Fig. 3 should be considered incidental.

Indeed, an effect of the projectile speed on the material response is revealed by the observation of delamination extent. In Fig. 7, the projected delaminated area measured in the present work (black symbols) is compared with the one verified in [4] for the same material (open symbols). In the abscissa, the maximum absorbed energy (coinciding with the perforation energy for the perforated samples, and with the impact energy for the non-perforated ones), is shown. Different symbols denote different panel thicknesses.

In general, for given energy and thickness, the delaminated area in the case of low velocity (LV) is sensibly larger than its high velocity (HV) counterpart. However, this statement seems to fail for $t=6 \text{ mm}$: quite interestingly, for this thickness the laminate behaviour is practically

independent of the bullet speed. For thickness values lower than 6 mm, the main parameter driving the phenomenon at high velocity is U_{max} , whereas the role played by the thickness is negligible. At low speed, the thinnest laminates ($t=1.5$ mm) exhibit the largest delamination extent, for a fixed value of the maximum absorbed energy. Indeed, the delamination propagation at low and high velocity seems to be governed by quite different laws.

Fig. 7: Delamination area against maximum absorbed energy, U_{max} .

CONCLUSIONS

From the results presented and discussed in this work, concerning the high velocity impact behaviour of stitched CFRP laminates, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

- the general trend of the perforation energy as a function of the panel thickness is in good agreement with the one found in low velocity impact;
- a main difference between low velocity and high velocity impact behaviour seems to be in the influence of the bullet diameter, which appears to be governed by different laws in the two cases;
- the delamination extent at high velocity is smaller than at low velocity, provided the panel is sufficiently thin; for thick panels, the effect of velocity tends to disappear.

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